

SOME ELEMENTARY ALGEBRAIC CONSIDERATIONS INSPIRED BY SMARANDACHE'S FUNCTION (II)

E. RĂDESCU, N. RĂDESCU AND C. DUMITRESCU

In this paper we continue the algebraic consideration begun in [2]. As it was sun, two of the proprieties of Smarandache's function are hold:

- (1) S is a surjective function;
- (2) $S([m, n]) = \max \{S(m), S(n)\}$, where $[m, n]$ is the smallest common multiple of m and n .

That is on \mathbb{N} there are considered both of the divisibility order " \leq_d " having the known properties and the total order with the usual order \leq with all its properties. \mathbb{N} has also the algebraic usual operations "+" and ".". For instance:

$$a \leq b \iff (\exists) u \in \mathbb{N} \text{ so that } b = a + u.$$

Here we can stand out:

- : the universal algebra (\mathbb{N}^*, Ω) , the set of operations is $\Omega = \{\vee_d, \varphi_0\}$ where $\vee_d : (\mathbb{N}^*)^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^*$ is given by $m \vee_d n = [m, n]$, and $\varphi_0 : (\mathbb{N}^*)^0 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^*$ the null operation that fixes 1-unique particular element with the role of neutral element for " \vee_d "-that means $\varphi_0(\{\emptyset\}) = 1$ and $1 = e_{\vee_d}$;
- : the universal algebra (\mathbb{N}^*, Ω') , the set of operations is $\Omega' = \{\vee, \psi_0\}$ where $\vee : \mathbb{N}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is given by $x \vee y = \sup \{x, y\}$ and $\psi_0 : \mathbb{N}^0 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ a null operation with $\psi_0(\{\emptyset\}) = 0$ the unique particular element with the role of neutral element for \vee , so $0 = e_{\vee}$.

We observe that the universal algebras (\mathbb{N}^*, Ω) and (\mathbb{N}^*, Ω') are of the same type:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \vee_d & \varphi_0 \\ 2 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \vee & \psi_0 \\ 2 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

and with the similarity (bijective) $\vee_d \iff \vee$ and $\varphi_0 \iff \psi_0$, Smarandache's function $S : \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is a morphism surjective between them

$$\begin{aligned} S(x \vee_d y) &= S(x) \vee S(y), \forall x, y \in \mathbb{N}^* \text{ from (2) and} \\ S(\varphi_0(\{\emptyset\})) &= \psi_0(\{\emptyset\}) \iff S(1) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

Problem 3. If $S : \aleph^* \rightarrow \aleph$ is Smarandache's function defined as we know by

$$S(n) = m \iff m = \min \{k : n \text{ divides } k!\}$$

and I is a some set, then there exists an unique $s : (\aleph^*)^I \rightarrow \aleph^I$ a surjective morphisme between the universal algebras $((\aleph^*)^I, \Omega)$ and (\aleph^I, Ω') so that $p_i \circ s = \zeta \circ \tilde{p}_i$, for $i \in I$, where $p_j : \aleph^I \rightarrow \aleph$ defined by $a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I} \in \aleph^I$, $p_j(a) = a_j$, for each $j \in I$, p_j are the canonical projections, morphismes between (\aleph^I, Ω') and (\aleph, Ω') -universal algebras of the same kind and $\tilde{p}_j : (\aleph^*)^I \rightarrow \aleph^*$ analogously between $((\aleph^*)^I, \Omega)$ and (\aleph^*, Ω) . We shall go over the following three steps in order to justify the assumption:

Theorem 0.1. *Let by (\aleph, Ω) is an universal algebra more compleze with*

$$\Omega = \{\vee_d, \wedge_d, \varphi_0, \bar{\varphi}_0\}$$

of the kind $\tau : \Omega \rightarrow \aleph$ given by

$$\tau = \begin{pmatrix} \vee_d & \wedge_d & \varphi_0 & \bar{\varphi}_0 \\ 2 & 2 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

where \vee_d and φ_0 are defined as above and $\wedge_d : \aleph^2 \rightarrow \aleph$, for each $x, y \in \aleph$, $x \wedge_d y = (x, y)$ where (x, y) is the biggest common divisor of x and y and $\bar{\varphi}_0 : \aleph^0 \rightarrow \aleph$ is the null operation that fixes 0-an unique particular element having the role of the neutral element for " \wedge_d " i.e. $\bar{\varphi}_0(\{\emptyset\}) = 0$ so $0 = e_{\wedge_d}$ and I a set. Then $(\aleph', \tilde{\Omega})$ with $\tilde{\Omega} = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_0, \bar{\omega}_0\}$ becomes an universal algebra of the same kind as (\aleph, Ω) and the canonical projections become surjective morphismes between $(\aleph^I, \tilde{\Omega})$ and (\aleph, Ω) , an universal algebra that satisfies the following property of universality:

(U) : for every $(A, \bar{\Omega})$ with $\bar{\Omega} = \{\top, \perp, \sigma_0, \bar{\sigma}_0\}$ an universal algebra of the same kind

$$\tau = \begin{pmatrix} \top & \perp & \sigma_0 & \bar{\sigma}_0 \\ 2 & 2 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

and $u_i : A \rightarrow \aleph$, for each $i \in I$, morphismes between $(A, \bar{\Omega})$ and (\aleph, Ω) , exists an unique $u : A \rightarrow \aleph^I$ morphism between the universal algebras $(A, \bar{\Omega})$ and $(\aleph^I, \tilde{\Omega})$ so that $p_j \circ u = u_j$, for each $j \in I$, where $p_j : \aleph^I \rightarrow \aleph$ with each $a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I} \in \aleph^I$, $p_j(a) = a_j$, for each $j \in I$ are the canonical projections morphismes between $(\aleph^I, \tilde{\Omega})$ and (\aleph, Ω) .

SMARANDACHE'S FUNCTION

Proof. Indeed $(\mathbb{N}^I, \tilde{\Omega})$ with $\tilde{\Omega} = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_0, \bar{\omega}_0\}$ becomes an universal algebra because we can well define:

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_1 & : (\mathbb{N}^I)^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^I \text{ by each } a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I}, b = \{b_i\}_{i \in I} \in \mathbb{N}; \omega_1(a, b) = \{a_i \vee_d b_i\}_{i \in I} \in \mathbb{N}^I \\ & \text{and} \\ \omega_2 & : (\mathbb{N}^I)^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^I \text{ by } \omega_2(a, b) = \{a_i \wedge_d b_i\}_{i \in I} \in \mathbb{N}^I \\ & \text{and also} \\ \omega_0 & : (\mathbb{N}^I)^0 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^I \text{ with } \omega_0(\{\emptyset\}) = \{e_i = 1\}_{i \in I} \in \mathbb{N}^I \end{aligned}$$

an unique particular element (the family with all the components equal with 1) fixed by ω_0 and having the role of neutral for the operation ω_1 noted with e_{ω_1} and then $\bar{\omega}_0 : (\mathbb{N}^I)^0 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^I$ with $\bar{\omega}_0(\{\emptyset\}) = \{\bar{e}_i = 0\}_{i \in I}$ an unique particular element fixed by $\bar{\omega}_0$ but having the role of neutral for the operation ω_2 noted \bar{e}_{ω_2} (the verifies are imediate).

The canonical projections $p_j : \mathbb{N}^I \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$, defined as above, become morphismes between $(\mathbb{N}^I, \tilde{\Omega})$ and (\mathbb{N}, Ω) . Indeed the two universal algebras are of the same kind

$$\begin{pmatrix} \omega_1 & \omega_2 & \omega_0 & \bar{\omega}_0 \\ 2 & 2 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \vee_d & \wedge_d & \varphi_0 & \bar{\varphi}_0 \\ 2 & 2 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

and with the simialrity (bijective) $\omega_1 \iff \vee_d; \omega_2 \iff \wedge_d; \omega_0 \iff \varphi_0; \bar{\omega}_0 \iff \bar{\varphi}_0$ we observe first that for each $a, b \in \mathbb{N}^I, p_j(\omega_1(a, b)) = p_j(a) \vee_d p_j(b)$, for each $j \in I$ because $a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I}, b = \{b_i\}_{i \in I}, p_j(\omega_1(a, b)) = p_j(\{a_i \vee_d b_i\}_{i \in I}) = a_j \vee_d b_j$ and $p_j(a) \vee_d p_j(b) = p_j(\{a_i\}_{i \in I}) \vee_d p_j(\{b_i\}_{i \in I}) = a_j \vee_d b_j$ and then $p_j(\omega_0(\{\emptyset\})) = \varphi_0(\{\emptyset\}) \iff p_j(\{e_i = 1\}_{i \in I}) = 1 \iff p_j(e_{\omega_1}) = e_{\vee_d}$; analogously we prove that p_j , for each $j \in I$ keeps the operations ω_2 and $\bar{\omega}_0$, too. So, it was built the universal algebra $(\mathbb{N}^I, \tilde{\Omega})$ with $\tilde{\Omega} = \{\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_0, \bar{\omega}_0\}$ of the kind τ described above.

We prove the property of universality (\mathcal{U}).

We observe for this purpose that the u_i morphismes for each $i \in I$, presumes the coditions: for each $x, y \in S, u_i(x \top y) = u_i(x) \vee_d u_i(y); u_i(x \perp y) = u_i(x) \wedge_d u_i(y); u_i(\sigma_0(\{\emptyset\})) = \varphi_0(\{\emptyset\}) \iff u_i(e_{\top}) = e_{\vee_d} = 1$ and $u_i(\bar{\sigma}_0(\{\emptyset\})) = \bar{\varphi}_0(\{\emptyset\}) \iff u_i(\bar{e}_{\perp}) = e_{\wedge_d} = 0$ which show also the similarity (bijective) between $\tilde{\Omega}$ and Ω . We also observe that $(S, \tilde{\Omega})$ and $(\mathbb{N}^I, \tilde{\Omega})$ are of the same kind and there is a similarity (bijective) between $\tilde{\Omega}$ and $\tilde{\Omega}$ given by $\top \iff \omega_1; \perp \iff \omega_2; \sigma_0 \iff \omega_0; \bar{\sigma}_0 \iff \bar{\omega}_0$.

We define the corespondance $u : A \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^I$ by $u(x) = \{u_i(x)\}_{i \in I}$.

u is the function:

- for each $x \in A, (\exists) u_i(x) \in \mathbb{N}$ for each $i \in I$ (u_i -functions) so $(\exists) \{u_i(x)\}_{i \in I}$ that can be imagines for x ;

- $x_1 = x_2 \implies u(x_1) = u(x_2)$ because $x_1 = x_2$ and u_i -functions lead to $u_i(x_1) = u_i(x_2)$ for each $i \in I \implies \{u_i(x_1)\}_{i \in I} = \{u_i(x_2)\}_{i \in I} \implies u(x_1) = u(x_2)$.

u is a morphisme: for each $x, y \in A$, $u(x \top y) = \{u_i(x \top y)\}_{i \in I} = \{u_i(x) \vee_d u_i(y)\}_{i \in I} = \omega_1(\{u_i(x)\}_{i \in I}, \{u_i(y)\}_{i \in I}) = \omega_1(u(x), u(y))$. Then $u(\sigma_0(\{\emptyset\})) = \omega_0(\{\emptyset\}) \iff u(e_\top) = e_{\omega_1}$ because for each $\{a_i\}_{i \in I} \in \aleph^I$, $\omega_1(\{a_i\}_{i \in I}, \{u_i(e_\top)\}_{i \in I}) = \{a_i \vee_d u_i(e_\top)\}_{i \in I} = \{a_i \vee_d 1\}_{i \in I} = \{a_i\}_{i \in I}$.

Analogously we prove that u keeps the operations: \perp and $\bar{\sigma}_0$.

Besides the condition $p_j \circ u = u_j$, for each $j \in I$ is verified (by the definition: for each $x \in S$, $(p_j \circ u)(x) = p_j(u(x)) = p_j(\{u_i(x)\}_{i \in I}) = u_j(x)$).

For the singleness of u we consider u and \bar{u} , two morphismes so that $p_j \circ u = u_j$ (1) and $p_j \circ \bar{u} = u_j$ (2), for every $j \in I$. Then for every $x \in A$, if $u(x) = \{u_i(x)\}_{i \in I}$ and $\bar{u}(x) = \{z_i\}_{i \in I}$ we can see that $y_j = u_j(x) = (p_j \circ \bar{u})(x) = p_j(\{z_i\}_{i \in I}) = z_j$, for every $j \in I$ i.e. $u(x) = \bar{u}(x)$, for every $x \in A \iff u = \bar{u}$.

Consequence . Particularly, taking $A = \aleph^I$ and $u_i = p_i$ we obtain: the morphisme $u : \aleph^I \rightarrow \aleph^I$ verifies the condition $p_j \circ u = p_j$, for every $j \in I$, if and only if, $u = 1_{\aleph^I}$.

The property of universality establishes the universal algebra $(\aleph^I, \bar{\Omega})$ until an isomorphisme as it results from:

Theorem 0.2. *If (P, Ω) is an universal algebra of the same kind as (\aleph, Ω) and $p'_i : P \rightarrow \aleph$, $i \in I$ a family of morphismes between (P, Ω) and (\aleph, Ω) so that for every universal algebra $(A, \bar{\Omega})$ and every morphisme $u_i : A \rightarrow \aleph$, for every $i \in I$ between $(A, \bar{\Omega})$ and (\aleph, Ω) it exists an unique morphisme $u : A \rightarrow P$ with $p'_j \circ u = u_i$, for every $i \in I$, then it exists an unique isomorphisme $f : P \rightarrow \aleph^I$ with $p_i \circ f = p'_i$, for every $i \in I$.*

Proof. From the property of universality of $(\aleph^I, \bar{\Omega})$ it results an unique $f : P \rightarrow \aleph^I$ so that for every $i \in I$, $p_i \circ f = p'_i$ with f morphisme between (P, Ω) and $(\aleph^I, \bar{\Omega})$. Applying now the same property of universality to $(P, \Omega) \implies$ exists an unique $\bar{f} : \aleph^I \rightarrow P$ so that $p'_i \circ \bar{f} = p_i$, for every $i \in I$ with \bar{f} morphisme between $(\aleph^I, \bar{\Omega})$ and (P, Ω) . Then $p'_j \circ \bar{f} = p_j \iff p_j \circ (f \circ \bar{f}) = p_j$, using the last consequence, we get $f \circ \bar{f} = 1_{\aleph^I}$. Analogously, we prove that $f \circ \bar{f} = 1_P$ from where $\bar{f} = f^{-1}$ and the morphisme f becomes isomorphisme.

We could emphasize other properties (a family of finite support or the case I -filter) but we remain at these which are strictly necessary to prove the proposed assertion (Problem 3).

b) Firstly it was built $(\aleph^I, \bar{\Omega})$ being an universal algebra more complexe (with four operations). We try now a similar construction starting from (\aleph, Ω^*) with $\Omega^* =$

SMARANDACHE'S FUNCTION

(\vee, \wedge, ψ_0) with " \vee " and " ψ_0 " defined as above and $\wedge : \aleph^2 \rightarrow \aleph$ with $x \wedge y = \inf \{x, y\}$ for every $x, y \in \aleph$. ■

Theorem 0.3. *Let by (\aleph, Ω^*) the above universal algebra and I a set. Then:*

(i) (\aleph^I, θ) with $\theta = \{\theta_1, \theta_2, \theta_0\}$ becomes an universal algebra of the same kind τ as (\aleph, Ω^*) so $\tau : \theta \rightarrow \aleph$ is

$$\tau = \begin{pmatrix} \theta_1 & \theta_2 & \theta_0 \\ 2 & 2 & 0 \end{pmatrix};$$

(ii) For every $j \in I$ the canonical projection $p_j : \aleph^I \rightarrow \aleph$ defined by every $a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I} \in \aleph^I$, $p_j(a) = a_j$ is a surjective morphisme between (\aleph^I, θ) and (\aleph, Ω^*) and $\ker p_j = \{a \in \aleph^I : a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I} \text{ and } a_j = 0\}$ where by definition we have $\ker p_j = \{a \in \aleph^I : p_j(a) = e_\vee\}$;

(iii) For every $j \in I$ the canonical injection $q_j : \aleph \rightarrow \aleph^I$ for every $x \in \aleph$, $q_j(x) = \{a_i\}_{i \in I}$ where $a_i = 0$ if $i \neq j$ and $a_j = x$ is an injective morphisme between (\aleph, Ω^*) and (\aleph^I, θ) and $q_j(\aleph) = \{\{a_i\}_{i \in I} : a_i = 0, \forall i \in I - \{j\}\}$;

(iv) If $j, k \in I$ then:

$$p_j \circ q_k = \begin{cases} \mathcal{O}\text{-the null morphisme} & \text{for } j \neq k, \\ 1_{\aleph}\text{-the identical morphisme} & \text{for } j = k. \end{cases}$$

Proof. (i) We well define the operations $\theta_1 : (\aleph^I)^2 \rightarrow \aleph^I$ by $\forall a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I} \in \aleph^I$ and $b = \{b_i\}_{i \in I} \in \aleph^I$, $\theta_1(a, b) = \{a_i \vee b_i\}_{i \in I}$; $\theta_2 : (\aleph^I)^2 \rightarrow \aleph^I$ by $\theta_2(a, b) = \{a_i \wedge b_i\}_{i \in I}$ and $\theta_0 : (\aleph^I)^0 \rightarrow \aleph^I$ by $\theta_0(\{\emptyset\}) = \{e_i = 0\}_{i \in I}$ an unique particular element fixed by θ_0 , but with the role of neutral element for θ_1 and noted e_{θ_1} (the verifications are immediate).

(ii) The canonical projections are proved to be morphismes (see the step a)), they keep all the operations and

$$\ker p_j = \{a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I} \in \aleph^I : p_j(a) = e_\vee\} = \{a \in \aleph^I : a_j = 0\}.$$

(iii) For every $x, y \in \aleph$, $q_j(x \vee y) = \{c_i\}_{i \in I}$ where $c_i = 0$ for every $i \neq j$ and $c_j = x \vee y$ and

$$\theta_1 \left(\left\{ \begin{array}{l} a_i = 0, \quad \forall i \neq j \\ a_j = x \end{array} \right\}, \left\{ \begin{array}{l} b_i = 0, \quad \forall i \neq j \\ b_j = y \end{array} \right\} \right) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} c_i = 0, \quad \forall i \neq j \\ c_j = x \vee y \end{array} \right\}$$

i.e. $q_j(x \vee y) = \theta_1(q_j(x), q_j(y))$ with $j \in I$, therefore q_j keeps the operation " \vee " for every $j \in I$. Then $q_j(\psi(\{\emptyset\})) = \theta_0(\{\emptyset\}) \iff q_j(e_\vee) = \{e_i = 0\}_{i \in I} \iff q_j(0) = \{e_i = 0\}_{i \in I} = e_{\theta_1}$ because $\forall a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I} \in \aleph^I$, $\theta_1(q_j(0), a) = \theta_1(\{e_i = 0\}_{i \in I}, \{a_i\}_{i \in I}) =$

$\{e_i \vee a_i\}_{i \in I} = \{a_i\}_{i \in I} = a$ enough for $q_j(0) = e_{\theta_1}$ because θ_1 is obviously comutative -this observation refers to all the similar situations met before. Analogously we also prove that θ_2 is kept by q_j and this one for every $j \in I$.

(iv) For every $x \in \aleph$, $(p_j \circ q_k)(x) = p_j(q_k(x)) = p_j\left(\left\{\begin{array}{l} a_i = 0, \forall i \neq k \\ a_k = x \end{array}\right.\right) = 0 \implies p_j \circ q_k = \mathcal{O}$ for $j \neq k$ and $(p_j \circ q_j)(x) = p_j(q_j(x)) = p_j\left(\left\{\begin{array}{l} a_i = 0, \forall i \neq j \\ a_j = x \end{array}\right.\right) = x \implies p_j \circ q_k = 1_{\aleph}$ for $j = k$. ■

The universal algebra (\aleph^I, θ) satisfies the following property of universality:

Theorem 0.4. For every $(A, \bar{\theta})$ with $\bar{\theta} = \{\top, \perp, \theta_0\}$ an universal algebra of the some kind $\tau : \bar{\theta} \rightarrow \aleph$

$$\tau = \left(\begin{array}{ccc} \top & \perp & \theta_0 \\ 2 & 2 & 0 \end{array} \right)$$

as (\aleph^I, θ) and $u_i : A \rightarrow \aleph$ for every $i \in I$ morphismes between $(A, \bar{\theta})$ and (\aleph, Ω^*) , exists an unique $u : A \rightarrow \aleph^I$ morphisme between the universal algebras $(A, \bar{\theta})$ and (\aleph^I, θ) so that $p_j \circ u = u_j$, for every $j \in I$ with $p_j : \aleph^I \rightarrow \aleph, \forall a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I} \in \aleph^I, p_j(a) = a_j$ the canonical projections morphismes between (\aleph^I, θ) and (\aleph, Ω^*) .

Proof. The proof repeats the other one from the Theorem 1, step a). ■

The property of universality establishes the universal algebra (\aleph^I, θ) until an isomorphisme, which we can state by:

If (P, Ω^*) it is an universal algebra of the same kind as (\aleph, Ω^*) and $p'_i : P \rightarrow \aleph$ for every $i \in I$ a family of morphismes between (P, Ω^*) and (\aleph, Ω^*) so that for every universal algebra $(A, \bar{\theta})$ and every morphismes $u_i : A \rightarrow \aleph, \forall i \in I$ between $(A, \bar{\theta})$ and (\aleph, Ω^*) exists an unique morphisme $u : A \rightarrow P$ with $p'_i \circ u = u_i$, for every $i \in I$ then it exists an unique isomorphisme $f : P \rightarrow \aleph^I$ with $p_i \circ f = p'_i$, for every $i \in I$.

c) This third step contains the proof of the stated proposition (Problem 3).

As (\aleph^*, Ω) with $\Omega = (V_d, l_0)$ is an universal algebra, in accordance with step a) it exists an universal algebra $((\aleph^*)^I, \Omega)$ with $\Omega = \{\omega_1, \omega_0\}$ defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_1 & : ((\aleph^*)^I)^2 \rightarrow (\aleph^*)^I \text{ by every } a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I} \text{ and } b = \{b_i\}_{i \in I} \in (\aleph^*)^I, \\ \omega_1(a, b) & = \{a_i V_d b_i\}_{i \in I} \end{aligned}$$

SMARANDACHE'S FUNCTION

and

$$\omega_0 : ((\mathbb{N}^*)^I)^0 \rightarrow (\mathbb{N}^*)^I \text{ by } \omega_0(\{\emptyset\}) = \{e_i = 1\}_{i \in I} = e_{\omega_1},$$

the canonical projections being certainly morphismes between $((\mathbb{N}^*)^I, \Omega)$ and (\mathbb{N}^*, Ω) .

As (\mathbb{N}, Ω') with $\Omega' = \{V, \Psi_0\}$ is an universal algebra, in accordance with step b) it exists an universal algebra (\mathbb{N}^I, Ω') with $\Omega' = \{\theta_1, \theta_0\}$ defined by:

$$\theta_1 : (\mathbb{N}^I)^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^I \text{ by every } a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I}, b = \{b_i\}_{i \in I} \in \mathbb{N}^I, \theta_1(a, b) = \{a_i V_d b_i\}_{i \in I}$$

and

$$\theta_0 : (\mathbb{N}^I)^0 \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^I \text{ by } \theta_0(\{\emptyset\}) = \{e_i = 0\}_{i \in I} = e_{\theta_1}$$

The universal algebras $((\mathbb{N}^*)^I, \Omega)$ and (\mathbb{N}^I, Ω') are of the same kind

$$\begin{array}{cc} \omega_1 & \omega_2 \\ 2 & 0 \end{array} = \begin{array}{cc} \theta_1 & \theta_0 \\ 2 & 0 \end{array}$$

We use the property of universality for universal algebra (\mathbb{N}^I, Ω') : an universal algebra (A, Ω) can be $((\mathbb{N}^*)^I, \Omega)$ because they are the same kind; the morphismes $u_i : A \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ from the assumption will be $\bar{s}_i : (\mathbb{N}^*)^I \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^*$ by every $a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I} \in (\mathbb{N}^*)^I$, $\bar{s}_j(a) = \bar{s}_j(\{a_i\}_{i \in I}) = s(a_j) \iff \bar{s}_j = s \circ p_j$ for every $j \in I$ where $s : \mathbb{N}^* \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ is Smarandache's function and $p_j : (\mathbb{N}^*)^I \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^*$ the canonical projections, morphismes between $((\mathbb{N}^*)^I, \Omega)$ and (\mathbb{N}^*, Ω) . As s is a morphisme between (\mathbb{N}^*, Ω) and (\mathbb{N}, Ω') , \bar{s}_j are morphismes (as a composition of morphismes) for every $j \in I$. The assumptions of the property of universality being provided \implies exists an unique $s : (\mathbb{N}^*)^I \rightarrow \mathbb{N}^I$ morphism between $((\mathbb{N}^*)^I, \Omega)$ and (\mathbb{N}^I, Ω) so that $p_j \circ s = \bar{s}_j \iff p_j \circ s = S \circ p_j$, for every $j \in I$. We finish the proof noticing that s is also surjection: $p_j \circ S$ surjection (as a composition of surjections) $\implies s$ surjection.

Remark: The proof of the step 3 can be done directly. As the universal algebras from the statement are built, we can define a correspondence $s : (\mathbb{N}^*)^I \rightarrow (\mathbb{N}^*)^I$ by every $a = \{a_i\}_{i \in I} \in (\mathbb{N}^*)^I$, $s(a) = \{S(a_i)\}_{i \in I}$, which is a function, then morphisme between the universal algebra of the same kind $((\mathbb{N}^*)^I, \Omega)$ and (\mathbb{N}^I, Ω') and is also surjective, the required conditions being satisfied evidently.

The stated Problem finds a prolongation s of the Smarandache function S to more complexe sets (for $I = \{1\} \implies s = S$). The properties of the function s for the limitation to \mathbb{N}^* could bring new properties for the Smarandache function.

1. REFERENCES

- [1] Purdea, I., Pic, Gh. (1977). *Tratat de algebră modernă*, vol. 1. (Ed. Academiei Române, Bucuresti)
- [2] Rădescu, E., Rădescu, N. and Dumitrescu, C. (1995) Some Elementary Algebraic Considerations Inspired by the Smarandache Function (*Smarandache Function I*. vol. 6, no. 1, June, p 50-54)
- [3] Smarandache, F. (1980) A Function in the Number Theory (*An. Univ. Timișoara, Ser. St. Mat.*, vol. XVIII, fasc. 1, p. 79-88)

DEPARTMENT OF MATHEMATICS, UNIVERSITY OF CRAIOVA A.I.CUZA, NO. 13, CRAIOVA
1100, ROMANIA